

Analytical Study of Tuman Buzdar Under the British Rule: A Historical Perspective

Muhammad Sadeeq Baloch
Scholar Department of History, Ghazi University, D.G. Khan.
Email: socsadeeq@gmail.com

Sohail Akhtar
Department of History, Ghazi University, D.G. Khan
Email: sakhtar@gudgk.edu.pk

Received on: 14-10-2022

Accepted on: 18-11-2022

Abstract

Buzdar is considered one of the important tribes of Dera Ghazi Khan and it remained under the colonial period with massive resistance against the colonial period. The Buzdar tribe is living on the border of Dera Ghazi Khan were a constant headache for the British administration. At first the Government has given the responsibility of financing the Buzdar Sardar and collecting taxes from the area under British control. Shortly afterwards in 1857, they were relieved this responsibility. In the same year, a punitive campaign was decided against Buzdars.

Keywords: Buzdar, Colonial, Dera Ghazi Khan, Resistance, Border, Tribal, etc.

Discussion

The entire strip on the west side of Dera Jat is connected to Koh-e-Suleman. The part mount Koh-e-Suleman adjacent to the western border of Dera Ismail Khan has a population of Pathans. Baloch tribes are living in the border areas adjacent to Dera Ghazi Khan District. Infact the Baloch who are separated by the Barohi majority area. They are dividing into two groups the Northern Eastern group of Baloch is the Kehchi plains, which extend to the northern mountain range of mountain Koh-e-Suleman. They live in Punjab's Dera Ghazi Khan District and Sindh's Jacobabad district. The Second group of Baloch lived in the South western region, which included Makran and large parts of Iranian Balochistan. ¹

These tribes in the border areas of India were living a kind of autonomous life under the influence of their respective chief. Looting was the practice of the tribes who usually practiced in the plains of Dera Jat. From 1818 onwards the North Western Frontier was the boundary between the Sutlej and the Indus rivers in the Indian Empire. Then in front of it was a wall of great mountain range which is called the natural border of India and through whose doors all the conquerors of Europe have entering India from time to time. According to British, the British such over the Indian empire would not have come to an end until it reached this great mountain range and in this British Colonialist first linked the Indian Empire between 1838-48 and its mountainous geographically paired with they defend his expansion to the west saying it was not for Political or Military purpose. Because British policy makers were

Analytical Study of Tuman Buzdar Under the British Rule: A Historical Perspective

reluctant to manage more territory, but there was factor that compelled them to move forward and the biggest motivation was the fear of Russia advanced towards India, which was ingrained in the minds of British politicians at the time. Sir Robert Sandman, who became the Deputy Commissioner of Dera Ghazi Khan in 1866, was a strong proponent of British advance policy. According to him, the British intervention in the border area is justified. The British want to give the areas of the border tribes that are not under the rule of Amir of Afghanistan that this advance has become necessary for us. It is imperative that in the events of a war with Russia, we must defend Afghanistan, Kabul, Ghazni and the areas adjacent to Kandahar. If I had been a supporter of non-expansion rather than a conciliatory initiative, I would still have considered it a mistake to confine ourselves to this small strip of independent tribes that lies between the state of Afghanistan and us.²

British army's crossed the Indus and seized Sindh during the great game. Following the triumph of Sindh in 1843 and the absorption of Punjab following the second Sikh War in 1849, British India's North West frontier grew far beyond its company's bounds. India marched across the Indus River to the foot of the rock mountain ranges that separate the plains of the Indus basin from Afghanistan's higher plateaus and Kalat. These mountain ranges, along with an offshoot of the western Himalaya on the Indus' east side (known as the Black Mountain), formed a vast irregular belt on independent or semi-independent territory, extending and then in a long stretch southward down the Indus valley to the Sindh seaboard near Karachi, measuring about 1200 miles including deflections.³

The savage marauding tribes occupied the above-mentioned strip of area, numbering over 200,000 fighting men equipped with buckler, sword, and matchlock, who were frequently at odds with one another, hounding the plains of Punjab and Sindh. They are a persistent source of danger for commerce caravans and the plains of British India's inhabited regions.⁴ Pathans in tribes live around and north of the Koh-e-Suleman, some of whom are self-governing and others who recognize the Ameer of Kabul as their ruler. Baloch people live south of the Koh-e-Suleman. A number of Baloch tribes obstruct this section of the Suleman Range. From North to South, these tribes are the Qaisrani, Buzdar, Khosa, Leghari, and Gorchani, none of whom live in Balochistan. While the Baloch of the Koh-e-Suleman share many characteristics with their Baloch counterparts throughout the rest of Balochistan, they also have their own set of customs and rituals, as well as their own dialect of Balochi. All tribes of the Suleman Range, including the Dareshak and Mazari of Rajanpur tehsil, are linguistically classified as eastern Balochs, and their language is known as Sulemani Balochi.⁵

The only significant distinction between the Sulemani dialect of Balochi and the Makrani and Rekhsani dialects is that the former has been influenced by the Sindhi and Saraiki peoples over the centuries, whilst the latter dialects have a significant Persian impact. Most of these tribes were likewise self-sufficient and proud of their ancestors. Sir Richard best captured the general character of these tribes when he said, "Now, these tribes are savages, noble savages perhaps, and not without a tinge of nobility and generosity, but they are still barbarians. They have nothing resembling government or civic institutions; they have little to no education; they have a supposedly defined region, but Mahamedanism, as they understand it, is neither better nor worse than the creeds of the world's wildest races. Blood for blood is the one major commandment in their view. They are never without weapons, whether they are grazing their livestock, driving beasts of burden, or tilling the soil.⁶ They are constantly at odds with one

Analytical Study of Tuman Buzdar Under the British Rule: A Historical Perspective

another. There isn't a man alive who doesn't have some sort of stain on his hands. Each person keeps track of his or her assassinations. Each tribe has a lifelong debtor and creditor account with its neighbor. They see retaliation and revenge as the most powerful of all duties. They admire gallantry and daring in others and admire it in themselves. Men from the same political party will stick by each other in times of danger. Hospitality is the foremost virtue in their minds.

The British policy

“However, the implementation of British policies was successful in Sindh and only partially successful in Punjab in the first phase. However, the political ramifications of the process were vague and essentially conflicting. The example in Dera Ghazi Khan, however, demonstrated the close correlation between investment in settled agriculture and investment during British control. That is to say, the commanders' investment in the canal had little to do with the goals and ideas that many British officials had assumed. Unfortunately, the ban on crossing the border affected the work of the Deputy Commissioner in the border tribes.⁷ The Commissioners of the Districts have never been allowed to risk their lives outside the boundary or dream of expanding it beyond its current limits. In other words, a British official told the tribesmen that they would be happy to see them if they wanted to meet us in a friendly manner, but that they couldn't return their calls and couldn't intervene if their hands were cut off at the discretionary line, and that they couldn't help them get the adjustment back, which could be beneficial to both of us. At the time, the appropriate sanctions imposed on them were not only unknown, but also harmful to British interests. The District Officers' hands are tied in order to effectively curb the expansion of the chiefs' political clout, through which the British official administers the state's business in the tribal areas. It is infrequently stated that Baloch are less likely to carry weapons when forming than to travel with their animals, as Richard Isac Bruce pointed out. Even the most liberal-minded Baloch leader took pride in his ability to raise a competent gorilla warrior clan.⁸

Robert Sandman as Deputy Commissioner Dera Ghazi Khan

When Lieutenant Sandeman took over as Deputy Commissioner of Dera Ghazi Khan Punjab, Robert Sandman was in a state of disarray. He was diligent and thorough in his judicial investigations and particularly successful in dealing with Jirgas or community of village or elders, an institution he later founded, despite his lack of legal education. Before joining Dera Ghazi Khan, he served in Peshawar in 1862. Between the Suleman range and the Indus River, the Dera Ghazi Khan District is around 200 miles long and 25 miles wide. In criminal or civil proceedings, the appellate judge, the district magistrate, the chief of police, the jail, the revenue department's bow, and the former chairman of each administrative committee's local objectives are all involved. Almost every bill had to be presented to the legislative counsel by the Deputy Commissioner of the border district.⁹ Many state papers were forwarded to him for review. In addition to all of these and other obligations, the frontier district officer was responsible for dealing with the border tribes, which was a serious and essential job. The district officer was already familiar with Sandeman's original responsibilities, but Dera Ghazi Khan provided him with new experiences at one point. The Baloch were extremely different from the Pathans, and Robert Sandeman had to cope with

Analytical Study of Tuman Buzdar Under the British Rule: A Historical Perspective

them. Despite the fact that both are warlike, vindictive, and predatory. The Pathan is a republican with a strong sense of leadership, and the Baloch believe it is their obligation to obey their tribe's leader. As a result, the Balochis are simpler to deal with than the Pathans, making them better equipped for first-hand experience with a peace and goodwill policy. Despite his multiple responsibilities, District Officer Robert Sandeman went on reconciliation. He discovered that the tribal system of the Baloch nations was fast deteriorating. The power of the chiefs (Tumandar) and headmen (Muqadam) in Dera Ghazi Khan was diminishing. Different divisions and sub-sections of the Balochs were at odds with one another, and some tribes were at odds with tribes beyond their bounds. In the state of Kalat, a civil war was waging between the Khan of Kalat and his confederating chiefs. Lieutenant Sandeman quickly grasped the issue. He saw in Tribe Chiefs' hereditary power a source of strength that, if preserved, could become a potential tool of Imperial rule. As a result, he focused his efforts on resolving existing disputes and restoring the Tumundars' standing and dignity. On the British side of the frontier, he first acquired control of the Baloch tribes. Sandeman was drawn to the unsatisfactory nature of the existing line, which in many cases divided the tribes into two parts, one under British control and the other outside and beyond it, which he considered a cruel injustice. So, he wasted little time in asking the British Government to change the boundary, but the boundaries of the local border system were so ingrained in the minds of the British Organizers at the time that their demand was turned down.

Close Border System vs. Forward Policy

Lord Lawrence's close border arrangement was in effect at the time. British officers were not required to cross official business boundaries under any circumstances under the new arrangement; instead, they would back up every step to extend the boundary and respond to any issue outside the state government if necessary. As a result, the maximum was to run a campaign called the near border system for noninterventionists beyond the edge. The Punjab Government has largely adopted Lord Lawrence's close border system in the intervals between spasmodic bouts of aggressiveness, content with carrying the civilization line of the hills and administering periodic punishment for attacks by our robber neighbors.¹⁰ According to T. H. Holdich, the close border system, which has been applied almost as much to Balochistan as to Punjab, has had the effect of keeping frontier officers completely ignorant of frontier geography and preventing them from engaging in dialogue with trans-border chiefs, which could have resulted in better mutual understanding.¹¹ "The method provided forth by the government for the Punjab border belonged to the Lawrence brothers in Lahore," argued A. B. Awan. One of the characteristics of this strategy was that Governments would never exercise administrative control over areas or borders. As a result, the tribes were to be immune from the British administrator's day-to-day interference in their affairs. Close Border System was the name given to this policy.¹² Since 1941, this has been the policy of non-interference in the Balochistan affair. When the British were humiliated in Afghanistan and Balochistan, they resolved to abandon the region, which they did until 1775-1776. Then Sir Robert Sandemen come the peaceful conqueror of Balochistan, who implemented a new policy called as forward policy. This was the policy of non-interference in Balochistan matters from 1941, when the British were humiliated by their defeat in Afghanistan and

Analytical Study of Tuman Buzdar Under the British Rule: A Historical Perspective

Balochistan, and decided to quit the territory, until 1775-76. Then, Sir Robert Sandeman came renowned as the peaceful conqueror of Baluchistan, who invaded Baluchistan with a new technique known as Forward Policy.¹³

Different people have conveyed this policy in different ways, according to Dr. Naimatullah Gichki. In Layman's terms, it means bringing the harsh tribal under their control without going to battle with them, physically conquering them, or antagonizing them through cordial interactions, trust building, and peaceful dealings. They inhabited the central places of power, connecting them to the chain of command and post while allowing them to conduct their own affairs through their chiefs, according to their own customs and traditions. The Political Agent controlled tribal traditions through a Jirga, employing the Frontier Crimes Regulations, a barbarian law under political agent. The Sardars were to appoint and supervise a tribal army known as Levies that would be paid by the government under the new arrangement.¹⁴

"Control of an autonomous tribe, territory, politically, militarily, and economically, without engaging in conflict with them and physically winning it, without provoking it in any way," says A. B. Awan. This is accomplished by personal contact, gaining their confidence, and providing patronage. In practice, this meant occupying a central point in large numbers well ahead of the mutually agreed-upon borderline, connecting them with fair weather roads and a chain of posts, and allowing the tribes to manage their affairs according to their own customs and working through their chiefs and sardars. The tribal sardars were supposed to enlist in the Government-paid levies, although they were still considered tribal servant.¹⁵ Sandeman, a Punish Political Officer of Dera Ghazi Khan's Baloch area from 1856, was in communication with the Bloch tribes of the Suleman Mountains, the Khan's subjects along the Punjab-Khanate border. Sandeman supported the "Forward Policy," informing the Punjab government about Baloch matters in order to intervene in the civil war between the Khan, the head of the Baloch Confederacy, and his chiefs.

In Mithan Kot on the 3rd of February 1871, a conference was held to address the administrative problems of Balochistan.¹⁶ The Lieutenant-Governor, Mr. Henry Davies, and the secretaries in the civil and military departments, the General commanding the Punjab Frontier Force, the Commissioner of the Dera Jat Division, and Captain Sandeman represented the Punjab, while the Commissioner, Sir William Merewether, represented Sind, and Colonel Payer, Political Superintendent of the Frontier, Upper Sindh, represented Sind. The conference was ineffective. Sir William was a firm believer in the Khan as supreme ruler, and that all transactions with his country's tribes had to be done via him. Sandeman, on the other hand, gained one point. His dealings with the Marris were acknowledged, and he was assigned to the Sind Frontier Officer as far as they were concerned. The Khan's feuds with his chiefs were left unaddressed.¹⁷

Military soldiers who wanted active service and decorations but didn't care about the logistics were the main proponents of the forward strategy. Civilian administrators were the principal proponents of the close-border system, who desired all the money they could get for the development of their districts in the interior of India, as well as protection from famine and other disasters. Military adventures on the border were seen as a waste of public funds by these guys. To appreciate the magnitude of the incremental changes, it is necessary to understand the current condition of affairs on the boundary in general, and particularly on the Dera Ghazi Khan Rajanpur border, when Sandeman assumed command of the district.

Analytical Study of Tuman Buzdar Under the British Rule: A Historical Perspective

The Close Border System was in effect, and Sandeman was in charge of Kalat's political issues following the Mithan Kot summit, and he took very bold actions toward the Baloch tribe's concerns. Sandeman took the fateful step of crossing the Border line into the hills, escorted only by a few Baloch Sardars and their supporters, signaling the end of the Close Border System. This was unquestionably the start of the actual Forward Policy.¹⁸ The winner of the rivalry between the Close Border System and the Forward Policy is the latter, because Russian advances in Central Asia provided validity to their arguments. Sir Robert Sandeman was dispatched to the Baloch tribes and the Khan of Kalat in 1874 to enhance British relations.

Sandeman's ideas were quickly evolved into an extensive system of administration that the British used in the tribal parts of Dera Ghazi Khan District. After a series of brutal engagements, the British government finally chose to abandon their direct conflict doctrine in favor of a divide-and-rule strategy. Tribal rivalries and disputes were stoked, and tribes were encouraged to battle one another. This policy has proven to be effective. Even then, the Buzdar, Khitran, and Marri tribes continued to fight the British, causing them great anxiety. Roberts Sandeman, Deputy Commissioner of Dera Ghazi Khan, visited with all of the tribal chiefs in order to get control of the situation, and he rewarded them with substantial favors on their chiefs. Ghulam Haider Gurchani was appointed as the tribe's chief. The British Government bestowed the title of Sir on Sardar Imam Bakhsh Mazari. Almost all of the region's tribal Sardars were favored in some way. They were given vast estates in exchange for their assistance. Sandeman lacked formal education, but he proved to be a capable administrator. In Dera Ghazi Khan, he introduced the Jirgas system, which allowed Baloch tribes to settle their issues among themselves. In some regions, this system is still in use. This area also contains the tallest mountain summit in Dera Ghazi Khan, Fort Munro. Sandeman gave this name in the name of General Munro, a Multan commissioner. They were given enormous estates. Sandeman lacked formal education, but he proved to be a capable administrator. In Dera Ghazi Khan, he established the Jirga system, which allowed Baloch tribes to settle their issues among themselves. In some regions, this system is still in use. This area also has Dera Ghazi Khan Fort's tallest mountain top. Sandman gave this name in the name of General Munro, a Multan Commissioner.¹⁹

- Sardar shall be the chieftain of his own clan.
- All development will be done with Sardar's input and approval.
- In each tribe, a levee force will be constituted, and all government officials will be under the authority of the Sardar, with the British Government paying their salary accordingly.
- Sardar will have the authority to appoint, determine the pay of, and even dismiss all government employees.
- The British Government's Political Agent would be tasked with advising Sardar on administrative and development matters.
- To suit their needs, the Sardar were given enormous acreages of agricultural land.
- If the Sardar chooses the sub-tribe elders (Muqadam) as administrative assistants, they would be paid a stipend/salary.

Responsibilities

Analytical Study of Tuman Buzdar Under the British Rule: A Historical Perspective

-
- All Sardar will be loyal to the British regime.
 - Every Sardar shall ensure that the men of his tribe do not rebel against the British Government.
 - Each Sardar will be in charge of maintaining perfect peace in his domain.
 - Whenever the British rule requires personnel, all Baloch Sardar will step forth with their tribe Lashkar to assist the Government.
 - If a British Government agent believes a Sardar is no longer loyal to the British authority, he is replaced with another prominent Wadera from the same tribe.

The Source of income

During British administration, the Baloch Sardar grew in power, and the Sardari, which had previously been a political democratic status, became a kingdom. If the eldest son is not psychologically unwell, he will be the tribe's next Sardar. The tribal chief's sources of income are listed below

- Sardar was given the best agricultural land.
- The tribal area's undivided land was nearly exclusively for Sardar.
- Sardar receives the sixth percent of every working Baloch's income.
- Because the Baloch in tribal areas are virtually exclusively animal raisers, 2.5 percent of the animals (sheep and goats) were sent to the Sardar home.
- The tribal men have been known to rob adjacent tribes on occasion. Sardar got the lion's share of the spoils.
- Whenever Sardar has a sudden need or financial stress, the ever-popular custom of Bejjari and Phodhi is performed together money for his needs.

Tribal Arrangement

In Dera Jat, the British succeeded the Sikhs whose grip on these areas was very loose. The Sikhs had a very little encroachment on the areas adjoining the Rivers Indus. On the contrary their sphere of influence was limited to the plains. They had considered being the ruler even in the vicinity of scattered Fortress in the country. So, Sikhs has never been successful in maintaining peace on the border. In all his long history they have failed to bring these troubled tribes under his control. Rebellious rebellion among the tribe led to their long running violence and refusal to pay taxes leading to armed battles with the rulers.²⁰

When the Punjab joined British in 1849 the Punjab Government was responsible for maintaining law and order in the areas. To ensure protection of the lives and property of the people living in the plains, who were in constant danger of tribal robbery.

According to Richard Temple the evil of the tribesmen was wickedness incurable. They accuse British fugitive of the Harboring and conspiring to Harbor fugitive for fear of justice and murdering and robbing British subjects. They accuse those attacking British troops and even killing British officers in Punjab. The British Governments used to protect its citizens from the onslaught of Dacoits keep trade routes open and maintain law and order at the border. The British had resorts to retaliation in order to give an impression of their strength to the noisy tribes. The border area was a vast and difficult due to mountainous terrain area in retaliation. The first step of the Punjab administration was defense plan. The next step was conciliatory effort to convince the tribesmen at the benefit of living in a friendly

Analytical Study of Tuman Buzdar Under the British Rule: A Historical Perspective

neighborhood. Many concessions were made to the tribal people for example free medical care was provided and along the border strip in which dispensaries was established. Tribal chiefs or Mailk or Jirgas are urged the British authorities to be included in the resolution of their disputes. Efforts were made to settle the tribal people on barren land. The tribes were encouraged to join the British army and they have been provided with allowances to refrain from invading.²¹ They were employed as guardians of the passages in their area and guardians of public order and the revenue from the trade with either relaxed or abolished. But the British government not makes an administrative effort to enforce the existing decree.

The revenue was collected from the newly settled areas but not as but not from them. Justice was not under the penal code of India. It was decided by the Jirgas and the elders of the tribe.²² In general the British government adopted three methods to bind them the Punjab border tribes to a rule of law. They would have been applied for the looted goods and blood would have been shed for the loss of lives. The British policy towards the tribes was to adopt a conciliatory approach to power. At first an attempt was made to establish friendly relations with prostitutes' allowances should be given. But when all this failed and the tribesmen continued their looting and then the only solution was to use force Punjab penal campaigns were in the form of relentless killings and destruction of crops and villages meaning that crime of a few miscreants as reward of entire tribe. The logical consequence of which was destruction and it was said that peace had been achieved. The British did not adhere to the rule of day.²³ The British troops were together in Taunsa and then moved to the tribal areas. The British army, aided by bartillery damaged Buzdar property in the same manner as Brigadier General J. S. Hodgson action destroyed the sherani operation on the boarder of Dera Ismail Khan in April 1853.²⁴

Conclusion

Buzdar was an important Baloch tribe during the British imperial period, which resisted the British military campaigns of advance into the tribal area after the annexation of Punjab, but later the formation and evolution of the Tamandari system ended this resistance. In the tribal administrative structure under the influence of the British system of Taman Buzdar, tribal organization, Jirga, local police system and other rules and regulations made their grip on the area effective based on the Tamandari system. Which had an impact on the social and economic life of the region. And these remnants are still there today.

References

-
- ¹ Ahmad Abdullah, the historical background of Pakistan and its people, Tanzeem publisher; Karachi, 1973, P.80
 - ²Arnola Keppel, The problems of North West frontier. Quetta, 1977.P.107
 - ³M, Y, Qaisrani the Tiger Trail in, the Herald, 1993.
 - ⁴ S, Richard, the Secretary to the Punjab Government, in the Memorandum to Governor of Punjab.
 - ⁵ Encyclopedia of Britannica, Volume, 21.P.95
 - ⁶ Ibad,.M, Y, Qasrani. P.21
 - ⁷ Imperial Gazetteer of India North West Province,1979
 - ⁸ T.H. Thorton, colonial Sir Robert Sandeman, IST edition, Gosha e Adab Queeta, 1977

Analytical Study of Tuman Buzdar Under the British Rule: A Historical Perspective

- ⁹ Richard Isac Bruce Notes on Dera Ghazi Khan
¹⁰ H. Caldwell Lipset, Lord Curzon in India, 1898-1903, London; R.A Everett & co.1903. P.30
¹¹ Dames, Popular poetry of Balochistan
¹² H. Hungerford Holdich, In the Indian Border Land, 1800-1900, London; Methuen & Co, 1900. P.30
¹³ A.B. Awan. In Balochistan Historical and Political Process, London, New Century Publisher. 1985. P.118.
¹⁴ Dr. Naimtullah Gichki, In Baloch; In search of identity. London, Wrigleys, 2015 P.100
¹⁵ A.B. Awan, Ibad, P.151-152
¹⁶ Prof, Muhammad Anwer Shaheen Qaisrani, In Baluchistan *Tareekh aur Mahzab (urdu)*, Quetta; Idra-e-Tadrees, 1994, P.172.
¹⁷ A.L.P, Tucker, In Sir Robert G. Sandeman; Peaceful conqueror of Macmillan Company, 1921., P.28
¹⁸ Richard Isac Bruce, in the forward policy & its results, London; Langmans, Green, & Co, 1900, P.26
¹⁹ Mehmood Marri, *Raj Rah Band*, Baloch Academy Quetta, 1979
²⁰ C. Collin Davies, the problems of the North West frontier 1890-1908; London, 1975, P.21
²¹ Munshi Charm Geet Tareekh District Dera Ismail Khan; Lahore, 1882, P.30
²² Ibad, Arnold Keppel, P.4.
²³ Ibad, C. Collin Davies P.26.
²⁴ Captain H.L. Nevills, campaign on the North West frontier; Lahore, 1977, P.27.